

The Effect of Perceived Usefulness and Perceived Ease of Use on Continuance Intention with Satisfaction as an Intervening Variable in E-Wallet Users in Yogyakarta

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Abstract: This study aims to analyze the influence of perceived usability, perceived ease of use and satisfaction on the sustainable intention of e-wallets in Yogyakarta. The technique used for sampling is the purposive sampling method, by sending questionnaires to 180 e-wallet users in Yogyakarta with 13 questionnaires rejected because they do not meet criteria. Hypothesis testing was performed using path analysis with the help of the IBM SPSS Statistic 26 program. From the path analysis, satisfaction partially mediates perceived usefulness with a direct effect of 0.187 and an indirect effect of 0.081 with a total influence of 0.268. In the perceived ease of use variable, the satisfaction variable also acts as a partial mediation with a direct influence of 0.214 and an indirect influence of 0.132 with a total influence of 0.346. The results showed that together perceived usefulness, ease of use, and satisfaction had a significant positive effect on continuance intention. Partial perceived ease of use, and satisfaction have a significant effect on continuance intention.

Keywords: Continuance intention, perceived usefulness, perceived of use, satisfaction

1. Introduction

Technology and information have developed increasingly sophisticated, nowadays technology has a major influence on the business sector and also consumer behavior. Information technology is a tool used by humans to help create, change, store, and communicate information. At the moment the success of an enterprise depends on the availability of technologies capable of integrating many functions. The development of this technology has caused many changes, one of which is shopping for goods or services online using internet-based applications, where shopping online has become one of the increasing activities in the world and especially in Indonesia.

E-wallet is an electronic money service that emerged due to technological and information developments, which can be used by the public to facilitate payment systems operated by payment systems through Quick Response (QR Code), Near Field Communication (NFC), and One-Time Password (OTP) (Afolo, 2022). The development of the marketplace has made electronic wallets (e-wallets) appear as a new payment method that can be made for online and offline transactions (Dzikira and Farida, 2021). In the context of e-wallets, ease of service can be integrated to make it easier for users to meet daily needs such as shopping, data packages, meals, online and offline payments, paying electricity bills, wifi, ticket purchases and so on.

Indonesia has many e-wallets that are popular among the public, such as Dana, Ovo, ShopeePay, GoPay, Link Aja, Jenius and so on. With the increasing use of digital wallets, many companies have provided this digital wallet service for various transactions. Data from goodstatas.id that shows the number of E-wallets most used in Indonesia in 2022, can be seen in the following data:

Figure 1.1: The Most Frequently Used Wallet in Indonesia (2022)

Based on figure 1.1, according to goodstata.id E - the most frequently used wallet in Indonesia, the most in the first position is the GoPay digital wallet company. GoPay is a digital wallet company affiliated with the Gojek Indonesia super application service that is used by 88% of Populix survey respondents as well as being the best-selling in Indonesia. GoPay is a digital wallet that can initially be used to pay for all Gojek services, but has now become an official means of payment at most kiosks in Indonesia. Some of GoPay's distinctive features include GoPay Diary, joint venture, Paylater, and so on. The second position is the Dana digital wallet, Dana is a digital wallet in Indonesia at this time, Dana is designed to make every non-cash transaction run quickly, practically, and still guaranteed where Dana has been used by 83% of Populix survey respondents. The digital wallet, which was founded in December 2018 by

Vincent Iswara, has four licenses registered with Bank Indonesia, including electronic money, digital wallets, remittances, and digital financial liquidity. Ranked third, Ovo has been used by 79% of Populix survey respondents. This digital wallet, which has received an electronic money license since September 2017, continues to grow from year to year. Shope Pay is in fourth position, a digital wallet with the slogan of the number one e-commerce payment method in Indonesia has been used by 76% of Populix survey respondents. ShopeePay as a digital wallet affiliated with Shopee has several mainstay features, including payments with QR codes, topping up balances and transfers to banks free of admin fees, to payments that are guaranteed security. The next position is held by Link Aja in fifth place with 30% of users, i. saku with 7% of users, OCTO Mobile with 5% of users, Doku with 4% of users, and Sakuku with 3% of users.

Figure 1.2: The Value Of Electronic Money Transactions Recorded By Bank Indonesia (BI)

Figure 1.2 shows the value of electronic money transactions recorded by Bank Indonesia (BI) with a total value of Rp 131.21 trillion in October 2022. This number jumped 33.14% compared to the previous month which amounted to Rp 98.55 trillion. The value of electronic money transactions also soared 89.94% compared to the same period a year earlier. In October 2021, the total value of electronic money transactions was IDR 69.08 trillion. In detail, the value of electronic money shopping transactions reached Rp 36.65 trillion. The value of electronic inter-money transfer transactions amounted to Rp 20.65 trillion. Then, the initial transaction value or when you first filled in electronic money was recorded at Rp 884 billion. The value of electronic money top-up transactions reached Rp 69.13 trillion. The value of electronic money transactions for cash withdrawals amounted to Rp 2.90 trillion. Then, the value of electronic money redeemed transactions amounted to IDR 1.01 trillion. Furthermore, the volume of electronic money transactions amounted to IDR 1.22 billion in October 2022. This number increased by 13.56% compared to September 2022 which was IDR 1.08 billion. The volume of electronic money transactions also increased by 62% compared to a year earlier. In October 2021, the volume of electronic money transactions was recorded at IDR 753.10 million. Meanwhile, the value of credit card transactions was IDR 28.34 trillion in October 2022. The amount increased by 1.85% compared to September 2022 which amounted to IDR 27.82 trillion. Then, the debit card transaction value was IDR 660.83 trillion in October 2022. This number

slightly increased by 0.43% compared to the previous month which amounted to Rp 657.97 trillion.

Although there is an increase in the use of e-wallets, there are still many people who do not believe in the benefits of e-wallets themselves, people consider e-wallets too burdensome for users because of admin fees, e-wallet features that are difficult for some users to understand, there is distrust of users when they have to verify accounts using ID cards, and the limited use of financial technology for people in the region certain because of inadequate supporting facilities. Therefore, this shows the need to explore variables that encourage or inhibit the intention of sustainable use of e-wallets in Indonesia.

The decision to reuse sustainably is based on the evaluation process of a product after consumers use the product, causing a perception of like or dislike for the product (Richowanto and Susanti, 2021). Perceived Usefulness, perceived ease of use, and satisfaction are things that can influence the consumer decision-making process on the intention to reuse sustainably in a service system or technology.

Puong et al., (2020) found that customer satisfaction can be an intervening variable in the relationship between perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use on continuance intention on e-wallet platforms in Vietnam. However, different results are found in Juniwati's (2015) research

where this study did not find the effect of intervening satisfaction on the relationship between perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use on online shopping platforms in Indonesia.

Previous research conducted by Sawitri and Giantri (2020) found that perceived usefulness has a positive and significant effect on continuance intention on the ShopeePay e-wallet. Another study conducted by Brahmanta & Wardhani (2021) also found the same results that perceived usefulness has a positive and significant effect on continuance intention. While different results were obtained in Sullivan Kim's research (2018) stated that perceived usefulness did not have a significant effect on continuance intention towards e-wallet.

Another factor that can influence the intention to reuse on an ongoing basis is ease of use. The effect of perceived ease of use on one-wallet users on continuance intention is shown by research conducted by Bazi et al., (2020) states that perceived ease of use has a positive and significant effect on the intention of e-wallet continuation. However, this is not in line with the results of research conducted by Humbari and Wiese (2019) revealed that perceived ease of use does not have a significant direct effect on the continuance intention of e-wallets.

Another factor influencing sustainability intentions is electronic satisfaction (e-satisfaction). Previous research discussing the effect of e-satisfaction on continuance intention was conducted by Alalwan (2020) stating that e-satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on the continuance intention of e-wallet. However, the results of this study are not in line with research conducted by Prahawan et al., (2021) which proves that e-satisfaction does not have a positive and significant effect on the continuance intention of e-wallet.

Perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use have been studied previously as antecedents of continuance intention, with satisfaction as the intervening variable. However, these studies still get conflicting or inconsistent results in one study and another. The conflicting results in previous studies suggest that this topic still needs further research, especially since the results come from regions in Indonesia and other developing countries. Therefore, this study was conducted with the aim to analyze the effect of perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, and satisfaction on continuance intention in Yogyakarta.

2. Literature Survey

1) Technology Acceptance Model (TAM)

Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) is one of the prominent theories in studying digital platforms, this theory developed by Davis et al., (1989) revealed the most influential model used to explain individual acceptance of the use of information technology. TAM can be used to understand the relationship between humans and the acceptance of technology through perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use. Perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use are the most important constructs for predicting the acceptance of information systems. (Cheong and Park,

2005) in (Kumala et al., 2020). TAM has become popular because it meets the theoretical characteristics of being simple, supported by data, and applicable to predicting the acceptance and use of new technologies in various fields (Rauniar, Ralvski, Yang, and Johnson, 2014).

2) Continuance Intention

Interest to use e - wallet Directly Sustainable Influenced by Perception Usefulness (Perceived usefulness) and Perception Facilities Use (perceived ease of use). Thing aforementioned Caused by that interest somebody deep interest use Directly Sustainable at one technology somebody aforementioned Consider and believe that one technology that Used can get Increased above Performance that Done with other words technology aforementioned useful, and technology that Used that Rated easy deep Use or no necessary Issued attempt its very big to Use (Brahmanta and Wardhani, 2021).

Continuance intention refers to the level of intention that an individual has to keep performing certain behaviors such as continuing to use a system on an ongoing basis. In the context of e-wallets, Shang and Wu (2017) define continuance intention as a user's intention to keep using e-wallets. According to Shang and Wu (2017) continuance intention indicators are as follows:

- a) Continuation intention
- b) Intensity of use
- c) Intensity of recommendations

3) Perceived Usefulness

Perceived usability can be defined as how much individuals believe that the use of technology increases their productivity in conducting transactions (Davis, 1989). According to Nurzanita and Marlina (2020), perceived usefulness is a person's belief in the decision-making process, when users feel the benefits, they will decide to use the technology. A technology that refers to providing maximum benefits such as improving performance and increasing productivity, will make individuals interested in using the technology because it means that the technology has high usefulness. According to Chi (2018) there are several indicators used to measure perceived usefulness, including the following:

- a) Performance improvements
- b) Increased productivity
- c) Comfort
- d) Increased effectiveness

4) Perceived Ease of Use

Perceived ease of use or perceived ease of use is the level of confidence of a person that using information technology will reduce effort and facilitate work (Shang and Wu, 2017). According to Moslehpour (2018) in his research said that perceived ease of use is one of the important elements of technology because people from time to time will like things that are simpler or do not need high enough and easier effort that will not interfere or reduce productivity, so that the easier a technology is to use, then users will also be better at receiving the technology. According to Hubert et al., (2017) there are several indicators of perceived ease of use are as follows:

- a) Ease of learning
- b) Ease of fulfilling wishes

- c) Ease of being skilled
- d) Ease of transaction

5) Satisfaction

According to Kotler and Keller (2016) "customer satisfaction is the degree to which a person feels after comparing (perceived performance or results) compared to his expectations". Consumers can experience three levels of general satisfaction, namely if the user feels the perceived performance of a technology is below expectations, then consumers will feel disappointed, but if the performance of a technology is in accordance with user expectations then the user will feel satisfied with the technology, and if the performance results on a technology used the perceived results can exceed the initial expectations then the user will feel the level of satisfaction or more fun. According to M. Amin et al., (2014) there are several indicators that can measure satisfaction are as follows:

- a) Satisfaction level
- b) Good performance
- c) Match expectations
- d) Pleasant experience

Based on the literature above, the researcher developed the following hypothesis:

- H1: Perceived usefulness has a positive and significant effect on Satisfaction.
- H2: Perceived ease of use has a positive and significant effect on Satisfaction.
- H3: Perceived usefulness has a positive and significant effect on Continuance intention.
- H4: Perceived ease of use has a positive and significant effect on Continuance intention.
- H5: Satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on Continuance intention.
- H6: Perceived usefulness has a positive and significant effect on Continuance intention through Satisfaction.
- H7: Perceived ease of use has a positive and significant effect on Continuance intention through Satisfaction.

The relationship between the variables discussed in this study can be seen in Figure 1.3.

Figure 1.3: The Relationship Between The Variables

3. Methodology

This study uses quantitative research methods that use statistical numbers in processing data and use explanatory methods with causal relationships. The population of this study is e-wallet users in the Special Region of Yogyakarta. The sampling technique in this study is using non-

probability sampling with the purposive sampling method. Purposive sampling is used because this study has several respondent criteria to be sampled criteria for respondents must be over 17 years old, have made transactions at least 3 times in e-wallets, and are domiciled in the Special Region of Yogyakarta. The sample in this study was calculated using the formula Hair et al., (2018) stated that the ideal sample size depends on the number of questions on the research indicator where the number of indicators is multiplied by 5 – 10 and the results must amount to at least 100. In this study, the sample used was 163 respondents. Data acquisition in this study used the distribution of questionnaires through several social media platforms with a likert scale of 4.

Data were analyzed using the Statistical Package for the Social Science (SPSS 16). The validity test is carried out by looking at the results of the r count $>$ r table. While the reliability test is seen from Cronbach Alpha $>$ 0.7 (Ghozali, 2018). Next, researchers conducted a descriptive analysis using the mean calculation of each indicator. Then, researchers conducted a classical assumption test using the normality test with the Kolmogorov Smirnov Test, the multicollinearity test, and the heteroscedasticity test. Testing the hypothesis of researchers using t Test, RTest, Path analysis, and Sobel Test.

4. Results and Discussion

Characteristics of Respondents

Table 1: Characteristics of Respondents

Variable	Frequency	%
Gender		
Male	65	39,9
Woman	98	60,1
Age		
>25 Years	10	6,1
17 - 25 Years	153	93,9
Status		
Working	21	12,9
Student	142	87,1
Number of Transactions		
>10 times	128	78,5
3 - 10 times	35	21,5
Type E - Wallet		
Dana	58	35,6
GoPay	16	9,8
OVO	8	4,9
Shopeepay	81	49,7

From Table 1 above, it can be seen that the majority of respondents in this study were women totaling 98 people (60.1%). The dominant age of respondents in this study was vulnerable aged 17-25 years with a total of 153 (93.9%). The status of respondents dominated in this study was 142 students (87.1%). As many as >10 times (78.5%) respondents made transactions while using e-wallets. It can be seen that ShoppePay is the e-wallet most used by respondents in this study 81 people (49.7%), second there are 58 people (35.6%), third there is GoPay 16 people (9.8%), and finally there is OVO 8 people (4.9%).

Table 2: Descriptive Statistical Analysis, Validity Test, and Reliability Test

Statement No	r-calculate	r-table	Cronbach	Mean Alpha
Perceived Usefulness				
				3,45
1 My performance improved by using the e-wallet app.	0,738	0,1528	0,702	3,26
2 My productivity has increased by using an e-wallet app.	0,716	0,1528		3,35
3 Transacting through an e-wallet application is more convenient than using cash.	0,705	0,1528		3,58
4 Transacting through an e-wallet application increases my effectiveness in transacting.	0,750	0,1528		3,61
Perceived Ease of Use				
				3,46
1 I found learning to use an e-wallet to transact was easy.	0,731	0,1528	0,703	3,34
2 The e-wallet application fulfilled my desire in transacting.	0,649	0,1528		3,33
3 I find mastering the use of e-wallet apps quick and easy.	0,763	0,1528		3,57
4 I find it easy to transact using an e-wallet application.	0,765	0,1528		3,63
Satisfaction				
				3,30
1 I compete with e-wallet apps.	0,746	0,1528	0,767	3,04
2 The e-wallet app works with good performance.	0,795	0,1528		3,36
3 The e-wallet app met my expectations.	0,794	0,1528		3,34
4 I am happy with my experience using the e-wallet application.	0,768	0,1528		3,47
Continuance Intention				
				3,20
1 I intend to keep using the e-wallet app for all transactions.	0,864	0,1528	0,781	3,12
2 I will use the e-wallet app as often as possible.	0,864	0,1528		3,13
3 I would recommend an e-wallet app to others.	0,782	0,1528		3,36

Table 2 above shows the results of the mean, r-table and r-calculate (validity), and Cronbach alpha (reliability) values. Researchers used the mean to determine the tendency of each respondent to use e-wallet applications. The mean value is used to see the average respondent's assessment of each statement submitted, done using a Likert scale range from 1 to 4.

From the mean results of the two independent variables above, it is known that perceived ease of use is the first position with a mean value of 3.46. This shows that respondents use e-wallets because they are easy to learn how to use, easy to make transactions, and can fulfill what respondents want in transactions. In addition, another factor in the use of e-wallet applications is the perceived usefulness of respondents who feel that the usefulness provided by e-wallet applications such as improving respondents' performance, increasing productivity, and increasing effectiveness is one of the reasons respondents use e-wallets on an ongoing basis.

The value of r – calculate all the indicators in Table 2 shows the results of r – calculate ranges from 0.649 – 0.864 > 0.1528 from r – this table concludes that all indicator statements in this study can be said to be valid. The Cronbach alpha value in this study also showed results ranging from 0.702 – 0.781 > 0.7 can be concluded all variables and indicators can be trusted (reliable) for further testing.

Classical Assumptions

Normality

Table 3: Normality Test Results

One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test	
	Unstandardized Residual
N	163
One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test 1	
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	,105c
One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test 2	
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	,200c

One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test 3	
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	,089 ^c

The normality test was carried out to determine whether the data used in this study was normally distributed or not (Ghozali, 2018). In this test, researchers used the Kolmogorov Smirnov Test method. In this test the data is said to be normally distributed if the value of Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed) > 0.05 and vice versa if the value of Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed) < 0.05 then the data is not normally distributed. Table 3 shows that in each test carried out the results show a value of > 0.05 it can be concluded that the data used are all normally distributed.

Multicollinearity

Table 4: Multicolonicity Test Results

Coefficients Tolerance VIF		
Multicollinearity I		
Perceived usefulness	,535	1,870
Perceived ease of use	,535	1,870
a. Dependent Variable: Continuance intention		
Multicollinearity I		
Perceived usefulness	,535	1,870
Perceived ease of use	,535	1,870
a. Dependent Variable: Satisfaction		
Multicollinearity II		
Perceived usefulness	,520	1,924
Perceived ease of use	,494	2,024
Satisfaction	,751	1,332
a. Dependent Variable: Continuance intention		

The multicollinearity test aims to test whether the regression model used has a correlation between variables or not. If the regression model is said to be good, then there should be no correlation between independent variables (Ghozali, 2018). This test looks at the results of tolerance values and variance inflation factor (VIF), if the tolerance value is more than 10% (0.10) and the VIF value is less than 10 (VIF < 10) then the model is free from multicollinearity. Table 4 shows the results where each variable in the model is free from

multicolonicity because the tolerance value is more than 10% (0.10) and the VIF value is less than 10 (VIF < 10).

Heteroscedasticity

Table 5: Heteroscedasticity Test Results

CoefficientsSig	
Heteroscedasticity I	
Perceived usefulness	,279
Perceived ease of use	,102
a. Dependent Variable: Abs_Res1	
Heteroscedasticity II	
Perceived usefulness	,062
Perceived ease of use	,885
a. Dependent Variable: Abs_Res2	
Heteroscedasticity III	
Perceived usefulness	,143
Perceived ease of use	,938
Satisfaction	,991
a. Dependent Variable: Abs_Res3	

This test aims to test whether the regression model has variance inequality from the residual of one observation to

another. heteroscedasticity testing in this study using the Park Test method. The criterion is if the significant value of the data is more than 0.05 (> 0.05) then, the data used in this study is homoscedasticity or heteroscedasticity does not occur. Table 5 shows the results of the sig values of each variable ranging from 0.62 – 0.991 > 0.05 it can be concluded that this model is free from heteroscedasticity.

Test the hypothesis

t test

The partial significance test (t-test) basically shows how far the influence of the explanatory (independent) variable individually in applying the variation of the dependent variable (Ghozali, 2018). This test uses a significance level of 5% or 0.05. As for the criteria that can be seen from the results of profitability on each variable, if t calculate > t table (1.96) then Ho is rejected and Ha is accepted and if the significance (Sig) < 0.05, then the independent variable is significant to the dependent variable.

Table 6: Test Results

Model		Coefficients			t	Itself
		Unstandardized Coefficients	Std. Error	Standardized Coefficients		
		B		Beta		
1	(Constant)	3,819	1,310		2,916	,004
	Perceived usefulness	,259	,120	,201	2,149	,033
	Perceived ease of use	,419	,116	,340	3,624	,000
a. Dependent Variable: Satisfaction						
2	(Constant)	-,110	,988		-,112	,911
	Perceived usefulness	,187	,090	,176	2,078	,039
	Perceived ease of use	,214	,088	,210	2,422	,017
	Satisfaction	,316	,058	,383	5,435	,000
a. Dependent Variable: Continuance intention						

Table 6 shows the result of the significance of the first hypothesis is 0.033 < 0.05 means H1 is accepted, and the calculated t value is 2.149 > 1.96 t table which means the effect is positive. Therefore, perceived usefulness positively and significantly affects satisfaction. The significance value of the second hypothesis is 0.000 < 0.05 means H2 is accepted, and the calculated t value is 3.624 > 1.96 t table which means the effect is positive. Therefore, perceived ease of use affects satisfaction. The third hypothesis is 0.039 < 0.05 means H3 is accepted, and the calculated t value is 2.078 > 1.96 t table which means the effect is positive. Therefore, perceived usefulness positively and significantly affects continuance intention. The significance value of the fourth hypothesis is 0.017 < 0.05 means H4 is accepted, and the calculated t value is 2.422 > 1.96 t table which means the effect is positive. Therefore, perceived ease of use affects continuance intention. The significance value of the fifth hypothesis is 0.000 < 0.05 means H5 is accepted, and the calculated t value is 5.435 > 1.96 t table which means the effect is positive. Therefore, satisfaction affects continuance intention.

However, the constant values in the model 2 table give negative results, this can happen because there is a considerable range of values between the independent

variable, the mediation variable, and the dependent variable. A negative constant value indicates that if the variables perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use and satisfaction are equal to 0 then the fixed value or initial value of continuance intention is -0.110.

Coefficient of Determination (Adjusted R Square)

The coefficient of determination is carried out to determine how far the model is able to explain the variation of the dependent variable. The value of the coefficient of determination between zero and one. A small value of the determinant coefficient indicates the ability of the independent variable to explain the finite dependent variable.

Table 7: Results of the Coefficient of Determination

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	,638 ^a	,407	,396	1,147
a. Predictors: (Constant), Satisfaction, Perceived usefulness, Perceived ease of use				

Table 7 shows that the result of the Adjusted R Square value of 0.396 (39.6%) means that 39.3% of the variation in the continuance intention variable is explained by the variables

satisfaction, perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use, where these results are still Far from number one and can provide a conclusion that the independent variable used in this study is still limited in explaining the variation of the dependent variable.

Path Analysis

Path Analysis is one tool to test the influence of mediator variables (intervening). Path analysis is an extension of multiple linear regression analysis. Pathway analysis can determine patterns of relationships between three or more variables and cannot be used to confirm or reject imaginary causality hypotheses (Ghozali, 2016).

In this study the mediating variable satisfaction will mediate the influence of independent variables (perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use) on the dependent variable (continuance intention).

Figure 4: Path Analysis Results

The picture shows the results of the path analysis in this study, it can be seen from the figure for the value of P1 = 0.259 is a direct influence of perceived usefulness on satisfaction. The value of P2 = 0.419 is a direct effect of perceived ease of use on satisfaction. P3 = 0.187 is the direct effect of perceived usefulness on continuance intention. The value of P4 = 0.214 is a direct effect of perceived ease of use on continuance intention. The value of P5 = 0.316 is a direct effect of satisfaction on continuance intention. The value of P6 is the value of the indirect influence of perceived usefulness on continuance intention through satisfaction, the value is obtained from the result of multiplying 0.259 (P1) x 0.316(P5) = 0.081. Based on calculations, it can be interpreted that direct influence has a value of 0.187 and indirect influence has a value of 0.081. From the calculation results obtained, showing that the indirect influence through satisfaction is smaller than the direct influence of Perceived usefulness on continuance intention, it can be concluded that the satisfaction variable is accepted as a mediating variable or in other words H6 is accepted. The P7 value is the value of the indirect influence of perceived ease of use on continuance intention through satisfaction the value is obtained from the result of multiplying 0.419 (P2) x 0.316 (P5) = 0.132. Based on the calculation above, it can be seen that the direct influence is 0.214 and the indirect influence is 0.132 with a total influence of 0.346. From the calculation results obtained, showing that the indirect influence through satisfaction is smaller than the direct influence of perceived ease of use on continuance intention, it can be concluded

that the satisfaction variable is accepted as a mediation variable or in other words H7 is accepted.

Sobel Test

Sobel test path I test is used to determine whether the satisfaction variable can mediate the indirect influence of the variables Perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use on the variable continuance intention. The mediating variable can be said to be significant if the result of the t-count is > 1.96.

Sobel Test Line I

Based on the Beta and Standard Error values in Table 6, it is known that the Coefficient of Perceived usefulness (X1) to satisfaction (Z), and the Coefficient of satisfaction(Z) to continuance intention (Y), obtained the Beta and Standard Error values of each variable as follows:

a = 0.259: Regression coefficient of the independent variable Perceived usefulness (X1) against the mediated variable satisfaction (Z).

b = 0.316: Regression coefficient of the satisfaction mediation variable (Z) against the dependent mediating variable continuance intention (Y).

SE_a = 0,120:Standard error of estimation a

SE_b = 0,058:Standard error of estimation b

	Input	Test	Test statistic	Std Error:	P – value
a	0,259	Sobel test	2,00	0,040	0,044
b	0,316	Aroian test	1,97	0,041	0,047
S _a	0,120	Goodman test	2,03	0,040	0,041
S _b	0,058				

Source: Calculator Sobel Test

Table 4.26 shows the result of the t-count value of 2.00 > from the t-table (1.96). So according to the results of manual calculations that satisfaction (Z) mediates the effect of perceived usefulness (X1) on continuance intention (Y).

Sobel Test Jalur II

Based on the Beta and Standard Error values in Table 6, it is known that the Coefficient perceived ease of use (X2) to satisfaction (Z), and Table 6Coefficient of satisfaction (Z) to continuance intention (Y), obtained the values:

a = 0.419: Regression coefficient of the independent variable perceived ease of use(X2) against the mediated variable satisfaction (Z).

b = 0.316: Regression coefficient of the satisfaction mediation variable (Z) against the dependent mediating variable continuance intention (Y).

SE_a = 0,116:Standard error of estimation a

SE_b = 0,058:Standard error of estimation b

	Input	Test	Test statistic	Std Error:	P – value
a	0,419	Sobel test	3,01	0,043	0,002
b	0,316	Aroian test	2,97	0,044	0,002
S _a	0,116	Goodman test	3,04	0,043	0,002
S _b	0,058				

Source: Calculator Sobel Test

From the results in Figure 4.3 shows the result of the t-count value of 3.01 > from the t-table (1.96). So according to the results of manual calculations that satisfaction (Z) mediates

the effect of perceived usefulness (X1) on continuance intention (Y).

5. Conclusions

This study aims to determine the effect of Perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use on continuance intention, Perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use on satisfaction, satisfaction on continuance intention, and Perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use on continuance intention through satisfaction. The object of this research is e-wallet users located in the Special Region of Yogyakarta. Based on the results of data analysis that has been tested in this study, it can be concluded that:

- 1) The variable Perceived usefulness is proven to have a positive and significant effect on the variable satisfaction directly, evidenced by the results partially. Perceived usefulness has a significance value of 0.000 smaller than 0.05. This result indicates that H_1 is accepted.
- 2) The variable perceived ease of use proved to have a positive and significant effect on the variable satisfaction directly, evidenced by the results of partial perceived ease of use having a significance value of 0.000 smaller than 0.05. This result indicates that H_2 is accepted.
- 3) The variable Perceived usefulness proved to have a positive and significant effect on the variable continuance intention directly, evidenced by the partial results Perceived usefulness has a significance value of 0.039 smaller than 0.05. This result indicates that H_3 is accepted.
- 4) The perceived ease of use variable proved to have a positive and significant effect on the continuance intention variable directly, evidenced by the partial results of perceived ease of use having a significance value of 0.017 smaller than 0.05. This result indicates that H_4 is accepted.
- 5) The satisfaction variable is proven to have a positive and significant effect on the continuance intention variable directly, as evidenced by the partial satisfaction results having a significance value of 0.017 smaller than 0.05. This result indicates that H_5 is accepted.
- 6) The variable Perceived usefulness to the variable continuance intention through the variable satisfaction shows positive and significant results directly or indirectly. Based on the results of path analysis testing, the magnitude of direct influence was obtained by $p = 0.187$, while indirect influence was obtained by $p = 0.081$, with a total influence of $p = 0.268$, where the results showed a direct influence coefficient smaller than the total coefficient. This result indicates H_6 is acceptable.
- 7) The perceived ease of use variable against the continuance intention variable through the satisfaction variable shows positive and significant results directly or indirectly. Based on the results of path analysis testing, the magnitude of direct influence was obtained by 0.214, while indirect influence was obtained by 0.132, with a total influence of 0.346, where the results showed a direct influence coefficient smaller than the total coefficient, where the results showed a direct influence coefficient smaller than the total coefficient. This result indicates H_7 is acceptable.

6. Future Scope

From the results of the research that has been obtained, there are several suggestions that can be conveyed based on the conclusions and limitations that exist in this study, including:

- 1) In the results of research conducted for the R^2 test, the results of independent variables are still quite limited to explain the dependent variable, therefore it is better in future studies to be able to examine more deeply the factors that can affect continuance intention and can add independent variables to strengthen in explaining the dependent variable.
- 2) In the next study, it is expected to be able to conduct research on the same aspects, but with different regional selections, so as to test the consistency of the results in this study.

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